

THEORETICAL VIEWS ON PROVERB IN GERMAN AND UZBEK

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Annotation: This article devoted to the theme proverbs on German and Uzbek languages. Furthermore, the latest theoretical concepts and views of famous linguists were given.

Key words: *paremiological, “ideal-confirming” , cognitive-ideals hypothesis, cultural experiences, therapeutic functions, privilege.*

Proverb meaning has been an issue in paremiological research for a long time. In this paper the cognitive linguistic theory of conceptual blending, or blending theory, is explored as a starting point in the discussion of figurative proverbs. This theory is combined here with the notion of ‘base meaning’. Furthermore, the concept of ‘extended base meaning’ is introduced as a ‘thick’ meaning description, especially useful when proverbs are discussed in relation to collective knowledge structures. Proverbs form the gist of what cultures consider of real concern to them (Lawal et al. 1997:636), presenting cultural undesirables and desirables, all of which betray the cultural models a culture lives by (Shore 1996). Honeck and Welge (1997:609) capture this as a “cognitive-ideals hypothesis,” consisting of “ideal disconfirming” and “ideal-confirming” proverbs. Ideal-disconfirming proverbs exhort people to shun undesirable behaviors and ideal-confirming ones propagate desirable cultural values. People of the same

culture transmit proverbs to posterity, and, above all, use them not only as a regulatory mechanism for their life, but also as a privileged mode of understanding.

As a branch of linguistics, the main focus of phraseology is on the study of the nature of phraseology and their categorical features, as well as on the laws of the use of phraseology in speech. The most important problem in phraseology is to distinguish phraseological units from those that are formed in speech (that is, to be unprepared) in speech, and on this basis to identify the features of phraseological units. Due to certain differences between idiomatic phraseologies, phraseological combinations, and stable sentences (proverbs and parables, other equivalent phraseologies), many researchers understand phraseology in two ways: narrow and broad[1]. When understood in a broad sense, the scope of phraseology includes proverbs and sayings, stable sentences typical of folklore, and some forms of communication (greetings, farewell sentences). However, the issue of a broader understanding of phraseology is still controversial. The main tasks or issues of phraseology are: to determine the sequence of phraseological content and, in this regard, to study the character of phraseology; description of homonymy, synonymy, antonymy, polysemy and variant of phraseologies; identify the words used in phraseology and their specific meanings; clarify the relationship of phraseology with word groups; determine their syntactic role; The study of the formation of new meanings of words in phraseological units and the principles of separation of other phraseological phraseological units, methods of their study, classification and description in dictionaries.

Proverbs can be situated within the tendency of humans to favor indirect communication. As such, proverbs can be classified along with metaphors, idioms, irony, hyperbole, and indirect speech acts (Gibbs 1994; Temple and Honeck 1999). As an indirect mode of speaking and understanding, proverbs offer their users the freedom to conceptualize indirectly what they would have thought

about twice before saying directly without offending their targets. Conversely, their targets are given to understand them by aligning two apparently different but cognitively similar states of affairs, depending for their resolution for the most part on metaphoric mappings.

As representing recurrently lived and deeply entrenched cultural experiences, proverbs are invoked to make sense of abstract and concrete everyday experiences. Proverbs have been shown to perform various functions in cultures, namely, stylistic (Lawal et al. 1997:637), pragmatic (Lawal et al. 1997; Honeck and Welge 1997; Temple and Honeck 1999), cognitive (Lakoff and Turner 1989; Honeck and Welge 1997), didactic (Fox 2004; Brown 2004), socio-psychological (Haas 2002), and even therapeutic functions (Al-Krenawi 2000). In particular, Lawal et al. (1997:637) showed how proverbs play an important socio-pragmatic function among the Yoruba, whereby being elderly correlates with the privilege to speak proverbially and with being respected by the young for this very privilege of speaking proverbially. For instance, In Uzbek proverbs “Daryo bo’yida quduq qazimoq» we can understand that it’s no use of bringing something where it is out of use[2]. But this very proverb is used in other three languages with proper names. To carry coals to Newcastle. (Nyukaslga ko’mir olib bormoq) Eulen nach Athen tragen. (Afinaga boyqush olib bormoq) The meaning of these proverbs shows that there is no use of carrying owls to Athens as it is the land of owls, coals to Newcastle where they are produced themselves. Some proverbs of these countries are similar in structure and meaning but differing from using words. For example, in German proverb “Besse ein Spatz in der Hand, 4nalyse Taube auf dem Dach” the birds Taube- a dove and Spatz-a sparrow are used in order to give the main meaning. But English people take this meaning generally and use a bird in this way.

A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush. Differing from others Uzbek people don’t use any bird in this proverb. They get this meaning with the help of

reality “Uzoqdagi quyruqdan yaqindagi o’pka yaxshi” In Uzbek proverb “Eshak makkaga borgani bilan halol bo’lmas” a Donkey is symbolized as the symbol of stupidity. But differing from this country German people use another animal – A monkey in this way “Ein Affe bleibst ein Affe werder Konig oder Praffe” (Maymun maymunligicha qoladi xoh shoh bo’lsin, xoh pop). But this very animal is characterized as the symbol of activeness and cunning in the Uzbek language. English people avoid using animals as the symbol of stupidity in their proverbs and take examples from real life: All are not saint that go to the church. (Cherkovga borganlarning barchasi avliyo bo’lavermaydi.) In proverbs the rhythm plays the main role to show the general meaning of it.

We will continue our observations and analysis on the invaluable treasures of the German and Uzbek languages - folk proverbs and sayings, their linguistic and cultural features. Indeed, these linguistic units also embody the culture, worldview, morals and ethics of both nations, the German and Uzbek peoples, and their attitudes to life, through which they can deepen the psyche, culture and worldview of the German and Uzbek peoples. we realize white[3]. The proverbs are extremely rich and diverse in terms of subject matter. Homeland knowledge, labor, professional, friendship, harmony, wisdom, alertness, speech, language and culture, love and affection, as well as issues such as the negative xi slate that featured a diverse population. For example: In German: “ Angst hat große Augen ” Literally translated: “Vahimaning ko’zi katta” Alternative translation: “Qo’rqqanning ko’ziga qo’shaloq ko’rinadi”.

We can see the exact and semantic equivalents of this ancient German proverb in the Uzbek language. Proverbs arise primarily from the customs, values, ethnic culture, lifestyle of the people and also covering the time and periods. In this proverb, people who look for guilt in other person than themselves are ridiculed too. Although the Uzbek equivalents of this proverb are stylistically different, they are synonymous in meaning[4]. Both proverbs are used in a

negative sense. Although the equivalents of this proverb are semantically synonymous, they have their own usage, situation in literary works or in oral speech. As we have seen above, we come across several Uzbek equivalents of each German proverb. This reflects the ethnic identity of both nations. It is also possible that one Uzbek folk proverb corresponds to several German folk proverbs.

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